

Library Services and Stakeholders Satisfaction: The Case of Shiyuan College of Nanning Normal University

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Abstract:

This study examines the relationship between library service quality and the satisfaction of students and teachers at Shiyuan College of Nanning Normal University. Using a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 377 students and 23 faculty members through a structured questionnaire based on four key dimensions of library service quality: Accessibility of Resources, Responsiveness of Library Staff, Condition of Physical Facilities, and Efficiency of Digital Resources. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis were employed to analyze the data. The findings revealed that all four dimensions were perceived as "very important" by respondents and were significantly correlated with user satisfaction. Moreover, the overall satisfaction level was rated as "very satisfied," indicating that the library services at Shiyuan College effectively meet the needs of its users. The study concludes that enhancing these four service quality dimensions can significantly improve user satisfaction. Based on the results, an evidence-based Library Service Quality Optimization Model and an implementation plan were proposed to sustain high levels of service quality and user satisfaction. The model includes strategies such as resource supplementation, staff training, facility upgrades, and continuous feedback mechanisms. These recommendations aim to support the college's mission of fostering information literacy and lifelong learning among future educators, while also providing a reference for other academic libraries with similar contexts.

Keywords: Library Service Quality, User Satisfaction, Accessibility of Resources, Physical Facilities, Digital Resources, Academic Libraries, Shiyuan College.

Introduction:

The impetus for this study stems from Nanning Normal University Teachers' and Students' College's critical role in teacher reform education and talent cultivation. As a core base for teacher training in Guangxi, the college prioritizes enhancing future educators' information literacy and lifelong learning capabilities. With the library undergoing significant digital transformation—diversifying services through educational literature databases, research platforms, and internship resources, understanding how these dynamic changes impact user satisfaction is essential. This research aims to identify factors affecting satisfaction (e.g., accessibility resource, staff) responsiveness, digital utility) to align library services with the college's mission of academic excellence and educational innovation (Thompson, 2020; Baffour et al., 2021).

Through direct engagement with the college community, it is observed that persistent gaps between library services and the specialized needs of teacher education. Faculty and students navigating teaching practicums, research projects, and qualification preparations frequently reported challenges: fragmented access to basic education (basic education) resources, inconsistent digital tool integration, and constrained physical study spaces. These firsthand insights—coupled with feedback on staff responsiveness and resource availability (Chen, 2018; Smith, 2019)—highlighted the urgency to tailor services. For instance, education majors' express frustration when internship materials are inaccessible online, underscoring the disconnect between the library's evolving digital infrastructure and practical pedagogical demands.

Beyond institutional observations, this study synthesizes diverse data sources to contextualize findings. Comprehensive literature reviews (e.g., Afthanorhan et al., 2019; Wang & Liu, 2018) established global benchmarks for library service quality, while local surveys and focus groups captured discipline-specific needs of normal students (normal students) and faculty. Additionally, I analyzed usage metrics of the college's digital platforms (e.g., educational research databases, e-book loans) and compared them with peers institutions' best practices. Stakeholder

workshops with librarians, department heads, and IT staff further clarified operational constraints and strategic priorities, ensuring recommendations address both universal service principles (Johnson, 2020) and the unique ecosystem of teacher training.

Significance of the study. Understanding the quality of library services as perceived by students and staff is crucial for enhancing their overall experience, and investigating student and staff satisfaction with these services allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of current offerings. This research focuses on examining the relationship between library service quality and the satisfaction of students and staff at Nanning Normal University Teachers' and Students' College, with a key contribution being the provision of actionable insights to improve library services at this institution.

Methodology:

Design

The study employed a descriptive predictive survey design. The goal of the study was to assess the quality of library services and determine its relationship to teacher-student satisfaction. Descriptive research design determines the level of quality services and level of student-teacher satisfaction of these library services. The correlation method established the influence of the library services on the student-teacher satisfaction. Furthermore, the four library services were considered as predictors of student-teacher satisfaction.

Environment

The study was conducted in Nanning Normal University Teachers' and Students' College. Nanning Normal University Library is comprised of four separate campus libraries: Wuming, Mingxiu, Changgang and Wuhe, with a total building area of 63,000 square meters. Taking "readers-oriented, teaching-oriented" as the motto, the library has provided a good platform for teachers and students to searching for literature and information with the aid of modern management, service concepts as well as its rich collection. It has introduced and opened nearly 80 databases in Chinese and foreign language, such as Elsevier SD, ACS, Springer, Emerald, Sage, ProQuest Education Database, EBSCO, CNKI, VIP, Wanfang, MOOC (massive open online courses) and Duxiu. The library has also built its own database collecting teachers' and students' work, and dissertation papers. The capacity of total volume has reached 328TB of digital resources and 40TB of storage devices. Rich kinds of literature based in printed and electronic forms guarantee all the students and teachers with academic and other resources for teaching and research, especially those teacher-education literature. It provides book lending services, indoor reading, reference and consultation, inter-library loan, document delivery, reader training, document retrieval training, and also provides mobile service through e-library and official WeChat platform. The library's opening time can add up to 105 hours within one week. The WeChat platform, mobile library, electronic resources, and information retrieval system are available 24 hours.

Participants

Given the 16,493 students and 1,024 teachers as of September 2023 at Nanning Normal University Teachers' and Students' College, it is essential to select a manageable sample that is representative of the entire population while being practical for research purposes.

Sample size. The study decided to use a quota sample of 200 respondents including 160 university students spanning different academic years and 40 teachers. To ensure representation, stratified proportional sampling was employed using the year level. Forty students and 10 teachers were considered from each year's level.

Random sampling technique was used to select representative samples using , the following inclusion and exclusion criteria: (a) Bonafide students or faculty members of Nanning Normal University Teachers' and Students' College; (b) Must be currently enrolled/employed at the college; (c) Must have used the library sources within the last three months (d) Must be willing to participate and sign informed consent. Any person who does not meet the conditions stated in the inclusion criteria will automatically be excluded from this study.

Instrument

The study used three instruments to gather data. The first instrument is the Demographic Information and behavior of using library services. This part includes 11 sections. It includes gender, age, status, years of work, educational

background, position title, grade, frequency of use of library, when one usually uses the library, the type of library services and which floor of the library building is mostly used. The questions are a checked list to get the respondents' demographic information and behavior of using library services. The second instrument that measures the quality of library services was adapted from Sheikh, A. (2014). The questionnaire gathered information on the four factors of Library service quality e.g., 1) Accessibility of Resources, 2) Responsiveness of Library Staff, 3) Condition of Physical Facilities, and 4) Efficiency of Digital Resources. The questionnaire has 29 questions asking respondents to indicate their opinions on the level of service quality for each factor. The data is measured using a 5-level Likert rating scale with the highest rating of five and the lowest rating of one.

The third questionnaire gathered information on student and teacher satisfaction level for quality of library services. The questionnaire has 12 items that ask for the respondents' level of satisfaction with quality of library services. Both questionnaires employed the 5-point Likert scale as presented in Table 2.

Table 1
Ranges of Ratings of the Library Service Quality and Satisfaction

Rating	Service Quality Level	Satisfaction level	Ranges of Rating
5	Very high Service Quality	Very high satisfaction level	4.21-5.00
4	High Service Quality	High satisfaction level	3.41-4.20
3	Moderate Service Quality	Moderate satisfaction level	2.61-3.40
2	Low Service Quality	Low satisfaction level	1.81-2.60
1	Very low Service Quality	Very low satisfaction level	1.00-1.80

Suggestions regarding improving the library service quality in Nanning Normal University Teachers' and Students' College were obtained through the one open ended question to collect some advice on improving the library service quality in Nanning Normal University Teachers' and Students' College.

Data Gathering Procedures

Pre-Data Gathering. To undertake the research project, permission from the dean of the Visayas' Graduate School of Education was required, along with a panel member's endorsement. To secure the Notice to Proceed, the researcher followed the compliance check list and submitted it to UV-REC for technical and ethical review. The Ethics Committee issued a Notice to Proceed Certification once it was authorized. The researcher can then move on to collecting data using the questionnaire,

Actual Data Gathering. Upon securing the Notice to Proceed Certificate from the Research Ethics Committee of the University of the Visayas - Institutional Review Board, data gathering began. Data gathering survey was done for two weeks in both online using Wechat Application and face-to-face manner to facilitate convenience to the respondents on how they wish to answer the survey. This is done in a referral recruitment manner which minimized the minor risk identified in the study, which is socio-economic risk, allowing the students to have enough time to answer the survey in their free and preferred time. The survey is administered not necessary within the educational institution, but it can be done even outside as long as they meet the criteria as presented in the research respondents inclusion criteria. In addition, respondents were only considered a full respondent when consent was provided through signing of the Informed consent form.

Post-Data Gathering. Upon completing the survey, the data were tabulated in preparation for the data analysis. Data was stored safely on a computer with a password, and only authorized personnel can access the data. Data was disposed of when the study is published.

Data Analysis

To facilitate the analysis of the data for this research the following statistical tools were used. In describing the profile of the respondents, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were applied. For the level of sports engagement and the level of mental well-being, mean and standard deviation were also applied.

To test the hypothesis of no significant relationship between sports engagement and psychological well-being, the Pearson r 's product moment coefficient was used. Multiple Regression Analysis was used to determine the predictors of satisfaction of the students and teachers on the library services quality.

Ethical Consideration

This study was conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki. This study was approved by the University of the Visayas Research and Ethics Committee with approval number NTPMAED2025-071, dated July 28, 2025. Participation in this study was voluntary and included faculty, students, and staff from the Shiyuan College of Nanning Normal University in Nanning. Prior to data collection, all participants received an informed consent form explaining the study objectives, confidentiality measures, potential benefits, and the voluntary nature of participation. Participants were assured that they could withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. No financial incentives were offered. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Results and Discussion:

This section discusses the results of the study based on the identified research problems. Discussion focused on the quality of library service and its relation to the users' satisfaction.

Quality of Library Services

The quality of Library services was measured through a questionnaire answered by both students and teachers, and the results are shown in Table 3. Generally, the results obviously revealed that library services were rated of high quality in all the four aspects, namely accessibility of resources, responsiveness of library staff, condition of library facilities and efficiency of digital resources. This may suggest that the library services have addressed the needs of students and teachers and the expectations of the institution.

Accessibility of Resources. This was rated as high quality. Also, the respondents believed that the library has rich paper resource collection, the convenience of resource retrieval, the standardization of shelf management, and the adaptability of opening hours. These factors work together to significantly improve the convenience.

Table 2

Level of Library Service Quality

Dimensions/Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Accessibility of resources			
1.The library's collection of paper resources is rich in variety, which can meet the needs of students and teachers	3.66	.533	High Quality
2.The layout of various literature resources in the library is reasonable and easy to find	3.73	.488	High Quality
4.The opening hours of the library meet the demand and are reasonable and convenient	3.56	.623	High Quality
5.Ability to effectively communicate current information to staff and students (telephone resources, training announcements)	3.70	.499	High Quality
6.The updating of resources can meet the needs	3.74	.481	High Quality
7.Provide services such as self-service inquiry, self-service borrowing and returning, etc.	3.74	.481	High Quality
8.Clear and reasonable borrowing and returning rules	3.70	.529	High Quality
9.The borrowing and returning procedures are simple and fast	3.74	.473	High Quality
10.Interlibrary borrowing and timely document transmission	3.75	.468	High Quality

Factor mean	3.66	.566	High Quality
Responsiveness of library staff			
1. Library staff is friendly, proactive	3.74	.475	High Quality
2. Library staff have the necessary knowledge and skills to accurately understand the needs of student and staff	3.75	.468	High Quality
3. Library staff are quick to respond to student and staff needs/questions.	3.68	.490	High Quality
4. The service provided by library staff is fast, accurate and trustworthy	3.70	.542	High Quality
5. Library staff meet the personalized needs of student & teachers. (e.g., Resource recommendations, learning tools)	3.70	.532	High Quality
Factor mean	3.72	.479	High Quality
Condition of physical facilities			
1.The library environment is elegant and has a cultural atmosphere, which is convenient for students and teachers to study/research at ease	3.75	.468	High Quality
2.The building space and seating are sufficient; desks, chairs, and cabinets are in good condition.	3.74	.459	High Quality
3.The electric lighting in the library is bright	3.62	.588	High Quality
4.The indoor temperature of the library is suitable	3.70	.503	High Quality
5.The library environment is clean and tidy, and the floors, walkways and toilets are in good sanitary condition	3.72	.490	High Quality
6.The signage inside library is complete and clear which helps users to find anything easily	3.68	.549	High Quality
7.Provide personal learning or group discussion space	3.65	.547	High Quality
Factor mean	3.69	.517	High Quality
Efficiency of digital resources			
1.The library website is beautiful, easy to find e-books, e- journals, e- newspapers, etc.	3.72	.522	High Quality
3.Accessability to any digital resources in the library anytime, anywhere	3.68	.556	High Quality
4.Effective collection and integration of network resources	3.74	.473	High Quality
5.Databases such as China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI), Duxiu Knowledge Database)	3.75	.468	High Quality
6.Electronic resources such as reading show e-books, super star e-journals, e-newspapers Easy access and quickly download	3.68	.609	High Quality
Factor mean	3.71	.522	High Quality
Grand mean	3.70	.385	High Quality

Note: $n=200$. Legend: 1.00 – 1.80 very low quality, 1.81-2.60=low quality, 2.611 – 3.40 moderate quality, 3.41 – 4.20 high quality, 4.21-5.00=very high quality.

Responsiveness of Library Staff. This was rated as of high quality. Also, the respondents observed that the library staff's friendliness and proactiveness, professional knowledge and skills to understand user needs, quick response to user questions, and civilized service demeanor were of high quality. The library staff of Shiyuan College has shown good performance in service responsiveness, including attitude,

professionalism, efficiency, and image. These factors build a positive service interaction environment, making students and teachers feel valued and supported, and thus improving satisfaction. It is hoped that the library will continue to strengthen staff training, maintain a high - quality service team, pay attention to user feedback on staff services, and continuously optimize the responsiveness of library staff.

Condition of Physical Facilities. This was rated also as of high quality. The respondents have seen the library’s elegant cultural atmosphere, sufficient and well - maintained building space and seating, with appropriate lighting and temperature. The library is generally clean and tidy, complete, and clear signage, and provision of personalized learning spaces were very important to the satisfaction of students and teachers.

The library of Shiyuan College has created a good physical environment to provide a comfortable and convenient physical space for students and teachers, which is conducive to improving their satisfaction with using the library. The maintenance and management of physical facilities, and improvement of the environment with the change of seasons and user needs, can further enhance the quality of the physical facilities.

Efficiency of Digital Resources. The respondents rated this factor as of high quality. This suggests that the library website’s ease of use, the adequacy of Wi-Fi and VPN resources, the convenience of accessing digital resources anytime and anywhere, the effective integration of network resources, the comprehensiveness of database resources, and the accessibility of electronic resources were very important to library quality service and the satisfaction of students and teachers.

The library of Shiyuan College has achieved good results in digital resources including the user - friendliness of the digital platform, the guarantee of network resources, the convenience of resource access, the integration of resources, and the richness of database content. These factors have met the digital resource needs of students and teachers in the information age, The development of digital technology updates and expands digital resources, pay attention to the feedback of teachers and students can improve the efficiency of digital resources.

In summary, the library has made commendable efforts in multiple aspects to enhance service quality. These dimensions contribute to the satisfaction of students and teachers, and continuous attention to these areas will further solidify the library’s role in supporting the academic pursuits of the college community.

Students and faculty members’ Satisfaction of the Library Service Quality

Students and teachers’ satisfaction with the library services was measured through a 12-item questionnaire. As shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Student and Teachers’ satisfaction with library service quality

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>How satisfied are you with...</i>	4.50	.702	Very satisfied
1. ...the responsiveness of library staff to your inquiries or requests?			
2. ... the courtesy and friendliness of library staff during your interactions?	4.16	.916	Satisfied
3.... the effectiveness of library staff in resolving any issues or problems you encounter?	4.45	.755	Very satisfied
4.... the level of assistance provided by library staff?	4.38	.714	Very Satisfied

5. ...the resources and services provided by the library (e.g., books, journals, databases, e-resources, etc.)?	4.46	.742	Very satisfied
6.... the quality and relevance of the resources available in the library?	4.39	.775	Very Satisfied
7.... the accessibility of library resources (e.g., ease of finding, borrowing, and returning items)?	4.48	.694	Very Satisfied
8.... the learning environment and atmosphere of the library? (quiet, comfortable, suitable for study)	4.46	.722	Very satisfied
9.... the condition and upkeep of library facilities	4.50	.695	Very satisfied
10.... the opening hours and convenience of the library?	4.50	.702	Very satisfied
11.... the use and operation of any technology or equipment (e.g., computers, copiers) provided?	4.60	.681	Very satisfied
12.... the overall value you receive from using the library's services and resources?	4.57	.684	Very Satisfied
Grand mean	4.45	.711	Very satisfied

Note: $n=200$ Legend: 1.00 – 1.80 is very dissatisfied, 1.81 – 2.60 is dissatisfied, 2.61 – 3.40 is neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, 3.41 – 4.20 is satisfied, and 4.21 – 5.00 is very satisfied

Respondents were very satisfied with the quality of the library services at Nanning Normal University's Shiyuan College. Specifically, they were very satisfied with the responsiveness of library staff to inquiries or requests. Also, they never experienced discourtesy or unfriendliness from library staff during interactions. Further, they were very satisfied with the effectiveness of library staff in resolving any issues or problems encountered and with the overall level of assistance provided. Furthermore, they were very satisfied with the quality and relevance of the available resources, and the accessibility of library resources such as the ease of finding, borrowing, and returning items. Additionally, they were very satisfied with the learning environment and atmosphere of the library, the condition and upkeep of library facilities and equipment, and the opening hours and convenience of the library. Moreover, they were very satisfied with the use and operation of technology or equipment provided by the library and with the overall value received from using the library's services and resources.

Supporting the findings, in the study of Wang (2023), the customer's satisfaction with the experience effect of service quality was high and basically meets the customer's psychological expectations, which indicates that the implementation of the service strategy had been realized in all aspects of the customer experience process. The results of the multiple regression analysis of Lim et al. (2024) revealed that customer perceived value, satisfaction, and service quality significantly influence customers' psychological commitment and behavioral intentions of continued use and recommendations.

The correlation between service quality and teacher and student satisfaction of the library of Nanning Normal University Shiyuan College

Table 4 shows the data on whether there is a significant correlation between the factors affecting library service quality and the satisfaction of teachers and students. The statistical analysis reveals a significant correlation between the identified influencing factors and the satisfaction of teachers and students with the library service at Nanning Normal University Shiyuan College. Specifically, the p-values for accessibility of resources, responsiveness of library staff, condition of physical facilities, efficiency of digital resources, and the overall factors were all .000, which is less than the significant value of .05. This led to the decision to reject all the null hypotheses for all variables.

Table 4

Correlation between student and faculty satisfaction and Library Service Quality

Independent variables	r value	p value	Decision	Interpretation
Students and Teachers' Satisfaction and Library Service Quality in terms of:				
Accessibility of resources	.672	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Responsiveness of library staff	.679	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Condition of physical facilities	.674	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Efficiency of digital resources	.744	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Library Service Quality	.755	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Legend: Significant if p value is $\leq .05$.

Also, the Pearson R-values ranged from .672 to .755, indicating a strong positive correlation. Therefore, accessibility of resources, responsiveness of library staff, condition of physical facilities, efficiency of digital resources, and the overall factors influencing the relationship between library service quality and faculty and student satisfaction are all significantly and strongly correlated with their level of satisfaction. This means that as the perceived quality and effectiveness of these factors increase, the extent of teacher and student satisfaction with the library service also increases substantially.

Significant correlations are expected, as these variables are fundamental aspects of library service that directly shape the user's experience. The provision of easily accessible resources ensures that users can efficiently find the materials they need. Similarly, responsive, and helpful library staff, well-maintained physical facilities, and efficient digital resources all contribute to creating a supportive and effective learning environment, thereby enhancing overall satisfaction. Thus, it is conclusive that the overall factors which influence the relationship between library service quality and user satisfaction are intrinsically linked to the reported satisfaction levels of teachers and students.

Supporting the findings, in the study of Khadka and Srijana (2022), research on educational service quality indicated that factors like resource accessibility and staff responsiveness significantly impact user satisfaction, highlighting the need for libraries to prioritize these aspects to optimize user experiences and institutional performance. The results in the study of Nursanti and Tomoliyus (2021) further showed that service quality and resource efficiency significantly affect user satisfaction and loyalty, which are crucial for an educational institution's academic support mission. Therefore, understanding and strengthening these correlated factors is vital for maintaining high-quality library services and supporting the academic success of teachers and students.

Predictors of Students and Teachers' Satisfaction of the Library Services

The four library services were hypothesized to be predictors of the students and teachers' satisfaction. The hypothesis was tested using multiple regression analysis. Table 6 presents the regression matrix.

The multiple linear regression analysis shows that the model is statistically significant ($F(4, 195) = 44.3$, $p < .001$), indicating that the four predictors together explain a meaningful portion of the variance in students' and teachers' satisfaction with the library. The coefficient of determination, $R^2 = 0.476$, means that about 47.6% of the variation in satisfaction is accounted for by the four service-components you measured. The correlation coefficient $R = 0.690$ suggests a strong relationship between the observed satisfaction scores and those predicted by your model.

Table 5

Predictors of Students and Teachers' Satisfaction of the Library Services

Model Fit Measures

Model	R	R ²	Overall Model Test			
			F	df1	df2	p
1	.690	.476	44.3	1	145	.001

Predictors	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	0.0964	0.2631	0.366	0.714
Accessibility of Resources	0.4501	0.0651	6.914	< .001
Responsiveness of library staff	-0.0150	0.0567	-0.265	0.791
Condition of physical facilities	0.3573	0.0753	4.745	< .001
Efficiency of digital resources	0.2673	0.0613	4.360	< .001

Looking at the individual predictors, the accessibility of resources emerges as the strongest and most significant positive predictor ($\beta = 0.4501$, $t = 6.914$, $p < .001$). This means that for every one-unit increase in the accessibility of resources (holding the other variables constant), we would expect satisfaction to increase by approximately 0.45 units. The condition of physical facilities is also a significant positive predictor ($\beta = 0.3573$, $t = 4.745$, $p < .001$), indicating that improved physical facilities are substantially associated with higher satisfaction. Similarly, the efficiency of digital resources shows a significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.2673$, $t = 4.360$, $p < .001$), meaning that better digital resource efficiency is linked to greater satisfaction, though its effect size is somewhat smaller than the previous two. On the other hand, responsiveness of library staff has a coefficient of -0.0150 ($t = -0.265$, $p = 0.791$), which is non-significant; thus, in your sample, staff responsiveness does not seem to meaningfully influence overall satisfaction when the other three factors are controlled.

In practical terms, the findings suggest that the key drivers of satisfaction in this context are how accessible the library resources are, the state of the physical facilities, and how efficient the digital resources are. Efforts to enhance satisfaction should therefore prioritize improving resource access (perhaps borrowing procedures, catalog usability, resource availability), upgrading the physical library environment (space, comfort, lighting, furniture), and strengthening digital resource efficiency (online platforms, search speed, remote access). The non-significant effect of staff responsiveness might imply that while staff behavior and availability are still important, in this institution they may be overshadowed by infrastructure and resource factors—or perhaps the variation in staff responsiveness across respondents was too small to detect an effect.

In sum, the model provides clear evidence that nearly half of the variance in satisfaction is explained by the four predictors, and among them, three are strong and significant. The staff responsiveness did not show significance which may imply a uniformly responsive. It may also suggest that investment in physical and digital infrastructure offers better returns in terms of satisfaction in your university's library context.

University students' satisfaction with library services and resources using the Kano model (Galagala, 2024) – This study of four state universities in the Philippines found that while students were generally satisfied with basic aspects of library services and resources, they expressed neutrality or dissatisfaction with performance and excitement aspects of library services and resources. This aligns with the finding that accessibility and facility/digital efficiency were important. It also suggests that higher order/excitement features may matter less or are not yet optimized.

A path to improve user satisfaction in Academic Libraries (Perera, Somaratna, Silva & Adhikari, 2025) – In a survey of the main library at the University of Colombo, Sri Lanka, 73 % of students were satisfied with collections, services, technology-based facilities, and the library website; but concerns remained regarding insufficient books, restricted access, outdated collection, and e-resource training. This underscores your result that condition of facilities and efficiency of digital resources matter for satisfaction.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that the quality of library services significantly influences students' and teachers' satisfaction, with accessibility of resources, condition of physical facilities, and efficiency of digital resources emerging as strong predictors. These findings emphasize that user satisfaction is largely determined by how well the library integrates accessibility, comfort, and technology to support learning and research. Although staff responsiveness showed no significant statistical effect, it remains essential in ensuring a user-friendly and supportive environment. Overall, the study underscores the need for continuous enhancement of library services to create a modern, inclusive, and technology-driven learning space that fosters academic excellence and lifelong learning.

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